

cyanidin was identified to be Delphinidin by its standard R_f values², colour reactions³ and λ_{\max} 545 nm, shift in AlCl_3 (25 nm). Periodate oxidation and the hydrolysis with emulsin suggested the glucose molecules to be in pyranose forms and linked through β -linkages. The anthocyanin was confirmed by direct comparison with its authentic sample isolated from *Verbena hybrida*⁴.

Compound B (*flavone aglycone*); yellow solid, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5$, m.p. 346°, gave negative Molisch test; λ_{\max} 269 nm and 336 nm; R_f value 0.88 in *n*-butanol; acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 5); KMnO_4 oxidation gave *p*-hydroxy benzoic acid and KOH fusion gave phloroglucinol indicating the presence of free hydroxyls at positions-4', 5 and 7. These positions were also shown by the colours given with NaHCO_3 (blue), methanolic ZrOCl (yellow) and vanillin-HCl reagent (pink) and confirmed by the bathochromic shifts with NaOC_2H_5 (56 nm in Band I), AlCl_3 (9 & 46 nm) and fused NaOAc (9 & 40 nm). Hence, the compound B was identified to be a 4', 5 : 7 trihydroxy flavone, i.e., apigenin.

Compound C (*flavone glycoside*); yellow crystals; $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_{10}$; m.p., 174°; gave positive Molisch test showing its glycosidic nature; λ_{\max} 268 nm and 335 nm. Hydrolysis with 10% H_2SO_4 gave an aglycone identical to the compound B and a sugar identified to be D-glucose. Oxidation with KMnO_4 gave *p*-hydroxy benzoic acid. The negative colour test with vanillin-HCl reagent and no shift in Band II with fused NaOAc indicated the position-7 to be glycosylated.

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Flavonoids from Flowers of *Hamellia patensa*

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HAMELLIA *patensa* (N.O. Rubiaceae) is a shrub of immense medicinal use, Presence of two anthocyanins viz. Petunidine 3,5-diglucoside and Malvidine 3,5-diglucoside have already been reported from the fresh flowers¹. In the present communication the authors wish to report the flavonoid constituents of the flowers of *H. patensa*.

The air dried flowers (about 2 Kg.) of *H. patensa* were extracted with acetone under reflux on

a steam bath. The acetone extract was concentrated to a syrupy mass and was poured in large excess of water. The water soluble and water insoluble fractions were separated. The water soluble fraction was concentrated and successively subjected to sexhelet extraction with petroleum ether, benzene and ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate fraction was concentrated and then adsorbed over a column of magnesol. Elution with ethyl acetate yielded two substances A and B. Both these substances gave positive Molisch's test. The purity of the substances was checked by P.C. and T.L.C.

The compound A crystallised from acetone M.P. 340-2° (d) $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_{11}$ when being hydrolysed yielded an aglycone M.P. 349-50° $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5$ which gave positive colour reactions (e.g., Mg/HCl) for flavonoids and was found to be identical with apigenin (M.P. U.V. shift, Co. chromatography, m.m.p. and super imposable I.R. spectra with authentic sample), and glucuronic acid as Sugar moiety (identified by paper chromatography with authentic sample). Compound A was thus characterised as Apigenin-7-glucuronide².

The compound B Crystallised from Methanol M.P. 188° $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_{16}$. On acid hydrolysis yielded an aglycone M.P. 316°, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_7$ identical with quercetin (by m.m.p. and co-chromatography with authentic sample) and sugars D(+) glucose and L(-) rhamnose (identified by paper chromatography with authentic sample). Hence compound B was identified as rutin³ by m.m.p. chromatography and super imposable I.R. spectra with authentic sample.

The water insoluble fraction of the acetone extract was chromatographed on a column of magnesol which was eluted with ethyl acetate. The eluate yielded compound C which responded positive test for flavones. It was recrystallised from acetone-methanol (3 : 1 V/V) m.p. 348-50° $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5$. It did not respond to Molisch's test. It was identified as apigenin by m.m.p., super imposable I.R. and co-chromatography with authentic sample.

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